

СЕКЦІЯ V
ПСИХОЛОГІЯ. ПЕДАГОГІКА. СОЦІОЛОГІЯ

**REVISITING THE LESSON STRUCTURE PROBLEM OF UKRAINIAN
AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION**

Shlenova M. G., Senior lecturer

M. Ye. Zhukovskiy National aerospace university «Kharkiv aviation Institute»

The prerequisite for the motivational provision of the lesson of Ukrainian as a foreign language is its pedagogical integrity and structural completeness. Art is inexhaustible at its core, and it predetermines a variety of applying methods, didactic tasks, and structural variations of the lesson.

The structure is a form of the lesson. The right chosen structure is one of the necessary prerequisites for ensuring the pedagogical effectiveness of any lesson.

When choosing a certain structure or a form of any lesson, a teacher of Ukrainian as a foreign language should consider its expediency first. The task of a language teacher is to choose a form of the lesson which will provide the highest pedagogical efficiency, i.e. the lesson should be pedagogically expedient. The expediency in a lesson structure means the logical reasoning of all learning situations, their smart connection into an entity.

The effective lesson of Ukrainian as a foreign language always includes a logical order. The main factor that connects all its structural parts is a set of tasks (goals). For example, the purposes of the lesson called «Genitive case. Lexical topic: at the hospital» are to form monologue and dialogical speech skills, to control the level of speech skills development, to teach someone to apply creatively the well-known speech clichés in non-standard situations; to form lexical and grammatical speech skills; to form listening and reading skills. In accordance with the complex of tasks, the structural organization of the lesson is chosen.

The purpose of the lesson is predetermined by those tasks, which should be solved in the process of studying Ukrainian as a foreign language. Thus, such purpose shouldn't include only educational tasks as educational and upbringing processes, as well as personal development of students, are inseparable parts of teaching.

It is important to have another special task for each lesson, in addition to the main purpose of it as to raising problems that would be interesting for foreign students so that to make them communicate and exchange opinions.

The availability of a clear purpose does not exclude elements of improvisation. There could be unplanned and unexpected situations at the lesson. If students have homework they should be systematically monitored. First of all, control is an incentive to learn. Secondly, testing the knowledge

includes a training function. It is important to check not only whether a student did homework, but also how successfully he/she managed to do it. Thirdly, the knowledge monitoring gives the teacher the opportunity to detect individual characteristics of a foreign student's perception of the language material. Fourthly, it is important for a student to feel self-confident.

Thus, all elements of the lesson are necessary for an educational process, but they shouldn't be permanent as it is necessary to implement the systematic approach in choosing a lesson structure.

Nowadays, integrated studies become increasingly widespread. These are lessons where blocks of knowledge from different subjects are combined. The same didactic purpose is realized by the joint efforts of two or more teachers of different subjects, e.g. Ukrainian as a foreign language + biology, scientific style + mathematics. The methodical organization of a modern lesson allows an invariant approach: the same didactic purpose, the same tasks are often realized with the help of different means.

It should be remembered that it is wrongful to deny the creative nature of organizing the educational process. Each lesson of Ukrainian as a foreign language is a result of a teacher's creativity. This creativity does not tolerate excessive standardization and pattern provides the novelty, originality, move away from tradition, overcoming stereotypes.

Consequently, the structure should be stipulated by optimizing requirements of an educational process, which can be realized by means of selecting the most rational system of methods, forms of working aimed to ensuring efficiency of teaching students. The difference or inappropriate functioning of one or another element of the system affects the change in the quality of the entire education system.